

The Impact of Air Pollution on the Spatial Distribution of Covid-19 Across Bulgaria: A Study Using Satellite and In Situ Data

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Abstract

As a respiratory disease, the epidemiological spread of Covid-19 may be influenced by atmospheric pollutants, particularly fine particulate matter. The aim of the present study is to examine the impact of air pollution on the spatial distribution of Covid-19. In this context, we utilize satellite data from the GOME-2 (onboard of Metop satellites series) and TROPOMI (onboard of Sentinel-5P) instruments, along with ground-based measurements, covering the period from June 2020 to July 2024, to construct the spatial distribution of particulate matter pollution over Bulgaria. Another significant atmospheric pollutant relevant to the Bulgarian context is NO₂. Using satellite data from the TROPOMI instrument, we develop the spatial distribution of NO₂. We analyze daily in situ data on the spread of Covid-19 across the 28 municipalities in Bulgaria in its correlation with the atmospheric pollutants. In this study, we present an assessment of the impact of the averaged pollution profile on the overall distribution of Covid-19 cases in the country.

Keywords — Covid-19, atmospheric pollution, remote sensing, TROPOMI, GOME-2

1. INTRODUCTION

The relationship between air pollution—particularly nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) and fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀)—and respiratory diseases, especially in the context of COVID-19, represents a critical and increasingly investigated research area. A growing body of evidence indicates that prolonged exposure to air pollutants compromises respiratory function, rendering individuals more susceptible to respiratory infections [1, 2], including COVID-19. Chronic exposure to PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, and NO₂ has been associated with structural alterations in the respiratory tracts and lung tissue, such as fibrosis and respiratory tract remodeling, which diminish the body's ability to mount an effective immune response to viral pathogens.

Particulate matter (PM) is classified by aerodynamic diameter, with PM_{2.5} comprising particles of 2.5 micrometers or smaller, while PM₁₀ includes particles up to 10 micrometers in diameter. These fine and coarse particles can infiltrate deep into the pulmonary system and, in some cases, enter the circulatory system, leading to systemic inflammatory responses and adverse health outcomes. Moreover, these particles often contain hazardous substances, including heavy metals, organic pollutants, and biological agents, which exacerbate inflammation and contribute to pulmonary damage.

Nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), a prevalent atmospheric pollutant in urban environments, is primarily emitted from vehicular traffic and industrial processes. Long-term exposure to NO₂ has been linked to diminished pulmonary function and the exacerbation of pre-existing respiratory conditions. Furthermore, NO₂ plays a key role in the formation of ground-level ozone and secondary particulate matter, further compounding respiratory health risks.

Individuals with pre-existing respiratory diseases, such as asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), exhibit heightened vulnerability to air pollutants and are at an increased risk of severe outcomes from respiratory infections, including viral pathogens like SARS-CoV-2. Given the significant health implications of air pollution, understanding its interplay with respiratory pathophysiology remains essential for informing public health strategies and mitigating adverse health effects.

Numerous studies have demonstrated that long-term exposure to elevated levels of PM_{2.5} and NO₂ can increase the

severity and mortality rates of COVID-19. Fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) can facilitate viral entry and replication within the respiratory system. These particles may act as carriers for viral pathogens, potentially leading to an increased viral load in the lungs. Moreover, PM_{2.5}-induced inflammation can exacerbate immune responses, impairing the body's ability to combat infections effectively.

Regions with high concentrations of NO₂ often exhibit a higher prevalence of respiratory diseases, and such pre-existing conditions can render individuals more susceptible to severe manifestations of COVID-19. Several studies have indicated that individuals residing in areas with elevated air pollution levels, particularly in urban environments characterized by high concentrations of PM_{2.5} and NO₂, face an increased risk of severe COVID-19 outcomes. These adverse effects include a greater likelihood of developing complications such as pneumonia, higher hospitalization rates, prolonged recovery periods, and increased mortality.

Furthermore, higher air pollution levels have been associated with a greater spread of COVID-19, likely due to the link between air pollution and weakened immune defense mechanisms. This may increase individuals' susceptibility to viral transmission and infections. The most vulnerable populations include children, the elderly, and individuals with pre-existing medical conditions. These groups are more likely to suffer from the combined effects of air pollution and viral infections, including COVID-19, highlighting the urgent need for targeted public health interventions in areas with significant air pollution exposure.

Satellite remote sensing has revolutionized the ability to monitor atmospheric pollutants and their impact on human health. Instruments such as TROPOMI and GOME-2 have proven invaluable for studying and assessing the effects of air pollution, particularly fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), and aerosols, as well as their correlation with respiratory diseases, including COVID-19 [3, 4]. Sentinel-5P, part of the European Space Agency's Copernicus program, is equipped with the Tropospheric Monitoring Instrument (TROPOMI), which provides high-resolution measurements of key pollutants such as nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), ozone (O₃), carbon monoxide (CO), methane (CH₄), and aerosols, derived through the Absorbing Aerosol Index (AAI). TROPOMI measurements of NO₂ have been widely utilized for mapping air pollution across cities and regions.

In urban environments, particularly in highly industrialized and densely populated areas, elevated NO₂ concentrations are often observed due to high emissions from traffic. As a result, an increasing number of researchers rely on these satellite data to investigate the relationship between elevated NO₂ levels and the prevalence of diseases such as asthma, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), and COVID-19.

One of the challenges in monitoring particulate pollution from space is the inability to directly measure dust concentrations, even within the total atmospheric column above a given location, unlike other pollutants such as NO₂, SO₂, CO, and O₃. Therefore, dust pollution is typically assessed using various indices, such as Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD), the Aerosol Index (AI), or the Absorbing Aerosol Index (AAI). Sentinel-5P can indirectly estimate particulate matter levels through AAI, which has been strongly correlated with PM concentrations. Studies indicate that regions with high AOD values tend to exhibit higher incidence rates of respiratory diseases due to the inhalation of fine particulate matter. Consequently, Sentinel-5P data are well-suited for analyzing and comparing areas with elevated NO₂ and particulate matter levels to mortality rates and severe COVID-19 outcomes across different regions.

The Global Ozone Monitoring Experiment-2 (GOME-2) instrument, onboard the MetOp-A, MetOp-B, and MetOp-C satellites operated by EUMETSAT, is another crucial tool for measuring atmospheric pollutants. GOME-2 provides global measurements of ozone (O₃), NO₂, CO, and AAI (Absorbing Aerosol Index), among others. It is one of the most widely used instruments for monitoring global NO₂ levels, offering comprehensive data for tracking pollution trends and their temporal evolution.

Assessments of Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) can be utilized to estimate particulate matter concentrations, as high AOD values are frequently associated with elevated PM_{2.5} levels, which have been linked to increased respiratory and cardiovascular diseases. Satellite data do not directly provide AOD values but instead report AAI measurements. AOD values can, however, be derived through model-based transformations [5], allowing for a more comprehensive evaluation of atmospheric pollution and its potential health impacts.

Satellite data from instruments such as TROPOMI and GOME-2 are essential for monitoring atmospheric pollutants, including PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, NO₂, and aerosols, as well as for establishing correlations between pollution levels

Quality Information System for the General Public [10]. Data on the distribution of COVID-19 cases have been obtained from the Open Data Portal, which provides access to Bulgarian public data in open and machine-readable formats. Population distribution data have been acquired from the National Statistical Institute.

For each month and each defined area, AAI values have been extracted to construct seasonal variation profiles for each year within the study period. Subsequently, averaged seasonal curves have been derived. By averaging monthly values for each year, the spatial distribution of dust has been determined for each area within the Bulgarian region.

Averaged AAI values have been further refined at the municipal level and classified into four categories. Given that GOME-2 data provide reliable information for larger areas but lack sufficient granularity for smaller urban regions, AAI data from TROPOMI have been used exclusively for Sofia to refine the classification.

For NO₂, monthly TROPOMI data have been averaged over the study period and subsequently classified into four categories at the municipal level. The final classification system combines both AAI and NO₂ class values for each of the 28 municipalities, resulting in seven composite pollution classes. These classifications are then compared with the distribution of COVID-19 cases across Bulgarian municipalities [11].

Ground-based measurement data from Bulgarian automatic Ground Measurement Stations (GMSs) have been utilized for PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, and NO₂; however, these datasets are available only for a limited number of major cities [12]. Graphical representations of the averaged PM₁₀ and NO₂ values for the period from June 2020 to July 2024 have been generated for each municipality with available GMS data. These pollution trends are then examined in relation to the distribution of COVID-19 cases.

3. RESULTS

The distribution of COVID-19 cases across the 28 Bulgarian municipalities, expressed as a percentage of the total population, is presented in Figure 2. Figure 3 illustrates the COVID-19 mortality rate per 100,000 individuals.

Fig. 2. COVID-19 distribution as a percentage of the population

Fig. 3. COVID-19 mortality rate per 100,000 individuals

Fig. 4. Averaged PM₁₀ from GMS

Fig. 5. Averaged NO₂ form GMS

Figures 4 and 5 depict the spatial distribution of averaged PM₁₀ and NO₂ concentrations across Bulgarian municipalities for the period June 2020 – July 2024. Due to data limitations, only 19 GMS provide PM₁₀ measurements and 13 GMS provide NO₂ measurements, restricting the ability to perform a comprehensive comparison between COVID-19 distribution and ground-based pollution data. To address this limitation, satellite-derived data are utilized.

Fig. 6. AAI distribution derived from GOME-2 data

Fig. 7. Averaged AAI derived from GOME-2 and Tropomi data

Fig. 8. Averaged NO₂ distribution obtained from Tropomi data

Fig. 9. Aggregated index of averaged AAI and NO₂

Fig. 10. Covid-19 distribution

Fig. 11. COVID-19 mortality rate per 100,000 individuals

Figures 6 and 7 present the distribution of AAI based on GOME-2 data and the averaged AAI derived from both GOME-2 and Tropomi datasets. Figure 8 illustrates the spatial distribution of NO₂ concentrations obtained from Tropomi data. Figure 9 displays the aggregated index, calculated as the sum of normalized AAI and NO₂ concentrations. Figures 10 and 11 present the spatial distribution of COVID-19 cases and the corresponding mortality rates (identical to Figures 3 and 4) using a GIS framework.

A comparative analysis of Figures 9 and 10 suggests a correlation between the combined influence of dust (AAI) and NO₂ levels and the distribution of COVID-19 cases across Bulgaria. However, the distribution of COVID-19 mortality exhibits a different pattern. In regions with larger and better-equipped hospitals, individuals tend to seek medical assistance earlier, resulting in more timely and effective treatment.

The preceding analysis provides an overview of the relationship between air pollution and COVID-19 distribution on a national scale. However, significant variations exist at the municipal level. In Bulgaria, Sofia is the only municipality containing a single large city. Within Sofia, six different GMS provide pollution measurements, enabling an analysis of intra-city pollution variability [13].

Figure 12 shows these differences in PM₁₀ and NO₂ for five GMS in Sofia for the same 4-year period.

Fig. 12. PM₁₀ concentrations from multiple GMS locations in Sofia

The city of Burgas is the only other urban area with three distinct GMS locations. Figure 13 presents the averaged PM₁₀ and NO₂ concentrations recorded at these stations.

Fig. 13. PM₁₀ concentrations from multiple GMS locations in Burgas

In contrast, the cities of Varna and Plovdiv each contain two GMS, though both stations in each city are positioned within the same urban sector, limiting the spatial differentiation of pollution levels within these cities.

4. DISCUSSIONS

In this study, the administrative boundaries of Bulgarian municipalities are utilized as the spatial resolution unit. This approach is justified by the structure of the national healthcare system, which allows Bulgarian citizens to access medical services anywhere within the country. Since hospitals are typically absent in rural areas, residents primarily seek medical care in larger regional centers. Consequently, epidemiological data related to disease prevalence and healthcare utilization are most relevant at the municipal level.

Among Bulgarian municipalities, Sofia City represents the only relatively homogeneous urban area. However, even within Sofia, available data only indicate the number of individuals who sought medical treatment in various hospitals rather than their precise residential locations. Although the previous section highlights notable variations in air pollution across different regions of Sofia, corresponding COVID-19 distribution data at an intra-municipal level remain unavailable.

As a respiratory illness, COVID-19 primarily affects lung function. The most significant pollutants influencing respiratory health are fine particulate matter (PM), particularly PM₁ and PM_{2.5}.

However, Bulgaria has only three official ground-based measurement stations (GMS) that provide PM_{2.5} data. One of the objectives of this research project is to improve data availability for PM₁ and PM_{2.5} in Burgas and Sofia. The present study does not incorporate data from these newly established monitoring systems, as records currently cover only a one-year period, limiting their statistical robustness.

The study's reliance on Absorbing Aerosol Index (AAI) as a proxy for particulate matter represents a methodological limitation. Research shows that satellite-derived aerosol parameters like AAI have fundamental constraints when estimating ground-level particulate matter concentrations. The relationship between columnar AAI measurements and surface-level PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ is inherently complex [14]. AAI represents the entire atmospheric column, while health-relevant exposures occur primarily at ground level. The vertical distribution of aerosols can vary significantly, with elevated layers contributing to AAI measurements but having minimal impact on surface air quality. Studies have shown that aerosols aloft captured by satellite measurements may not be representative of ground-level exposure conditions [15]. The AAI signal can be influenced by long-range transport of aerosols from distant sources, potentially confounding the relationship with local pollution sources and health outcomes. Desert dust and smoke from biomass burning can contribute to AAI measurements while having different health implications compared to urban particulate pollution [16]. The relationship between AAI and surface PM concentrations also is highly dependent on atmospheric conditions including boundary layer height, relative humidity, and meteorological mixing patterns. These factors can cause temporal and spatial variability in the AAI-PM relationship that may not be adequately captured in the municipal-level analysis [17].

The spatial resolution limitations of satellite products create several interpretation challenges at the municipal level such as Scale Mismatch: GOME-2 data have relatively coarse spatial resolution (40 km × 40 km for MetOp-A and 80 km × 40 km for MetOp-B and MetOp-C), which may not adequately capture pollution gradients within Bulgarian municipalities. This resolution limitation is particularly problematic for smaller municipalities where a single satellite pixel may encompass multiple land use types and pollution sources [18]. The averaging of satellite measurements over municipal boundaries can mask important intra-municipal variations in pollution exposure. Studies have shown that spatial aggregation of satellite data can lead to exposure misclassification in epidemiological studies, potentially underestimating or overestimating health effects depending on the distribution of population and pollution sources within administrative boundaries [19]. Satellite measurements can be affected by surface brightness and urban heat island effects, which may introduce systematic biases in pollution estimates over urban areas compared to rural regions. These effects could systematically influence the relationship between satellite-derived pollution indices and health outcomes across different types of municipalities [18].

Satellite measurements are affected by cloud cover, snow, and other atmospheric conditions that create data gaps. These missing data are not randomly distributed, potentially introducing systematic biases in pollution exposure estimates. Areas with frequent cloud cover may have systematically different pollution profiles that are not captured in the analysis [20]. Polar-orbiting satellites provide only once-daily measurements at specific overpass times, which may not be representative of diurnal pollution patterns. This limitation is particularly important for NO₂, which exhibits strong diurnal variation due to traffic and industrial emission patterns [21].

These limitations have several implications for interpreting results at the municipal level. The combination of spatial resolution constraints and indirect measurement approaches may lead to exposure misclassification, potentially attenuating the observed associations between pollution and COVID-19 distribution. The magnitude of this bias may vary systematically across municipalities depending on their size, population density, and pollution source characteristics [19]. The coarse resolution of satellite data may not adequately control for within-municipality variations in socioeconomic factors, healthcare access, and other potential confounders that could influence both pollution exposure and COVID-19 outcomes. The study period (June 2020 to July 2024) includes periods with varying data availability and quality, which may introduce temporal biases in the pollution-health relationship assessment.

CONCLUSION

The present study provides a comprehensive assessment of the spatial distribution of COVID-19 cases across 28 Bulgarian municipalities during the period from June 2020 to July 2024, utilizing seven composite pollution classes derived from satellite data at a spatial resolution of 1° across 17 distinct geographic areas. Ground-based monitoring was limited, with only 19 Ground Measurement Stations (GMS) reporting PM₁₀ data and 13 stations providing NO₂ measurements, while just three official stations nationwide monitored PM_{2.5}—the pollutant most relevant to respiratory health. Notably, six GMS in Sofia and three in Burgas facilitated intra-city pollution analyses. Despite the robust dataset, several methodological limitations must be recognized. The scarcity of ground-based monitoring stations constrains the spatial granularity and accuracy of exposure assessments. Moreover, the coarse spatial resolution of satellite-derived data (ranging from 40 to 80 km by 40 km for GOME-2) may obscure smaller-scale pollution gradients critical for health impact analyses. The reliance on the Absorbing Aerosol Index (AAI) as a surrogate for particulate matter introduces uncertainty, given that AAI reflects columnar atmospheric concentrations rather than ground-level exposure. Additionally, data quality fluctuated due to atmospheric conditions such as cloud cover, and healthcare system factors further confound mortality patterns by influencing treatment accessibility and outcomes. The absence of sub-municipal COVID-19 data limits the finer-scale epidemiological interpretation of pollution-related health risks. Looking forward, the expansion of monitoring infrastructure—particularly targeting PM₁ and PM_{2.5}—is imperative. Technological advancements should focus on integrating higher-resolution satellite observations and refining algorithms to enhance conversion to surface-level pollutant concentrations, coupled with the assimilation of meteorological variables to better characterize pollutant dispersion and human exposure. Methodologically, future investigations must also account for healthcare system disparities, socioeconomic confounders, and population mobility to disentangle environmental from non-environmental factors influencing disease outcomes. The continuation of long-term surveillance will bolster statistical robustness and support the evaluation of temporal trends. Overall, this study balances the demonstration of promising associations with recognition of inherent limitations, thereby underscoring the necessity of sustained research efforts and infrastructure development to address environmental health challenges in Bulgaria.

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